

MAPLE TIZIMI INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA MATEMATIKA TA'LIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. Asosiy matematik tayyorgarliksiz texnik oliy o'quv yurtlarining zamonaviy bitiruvchisi o'z ishida yuzaga keladigan ilmiy, texnik va kasbiy muammolarni hal qilish va tahlil qilish imkoniyatiga ega emas. Bu esa matematikani chuqur bilishni, matematik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishni, amaliy masalalarni yechishda matematik qobiliyatlar bilan bir qatorda o'quvchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishni taqozo etadi. Shunday qilib, kasbiy muammolarni hal qilishda matematik qobiliyatlarni maqsadli shakllantirish talabalarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini samarali shakllantirishning zarur shartidir.

Kalit so'zlar: Analitik, silindr, parabolik, matematik paket, masala, Maple, zamonaviy, *simplify, plots, format, tizim.*

Аннотация. Без базовой математической подготовки современный выпускник технического вуза не способен эффективно решать и анализировать научные, технические и профессиональные задачи, возникающие в его деятельности. Это, в свою очередь, требует глубокого знания математики, развития математических способностей, а также формирования профессиональной компетентности студентов наряду с развитием их математических навыков при решении прикладных задач. Таким образом, целенаправленное формирование математических способностей при решении профессиональных задач является необходимым условием для эффективного формирования профессиональной компетентности студентов.

Ключевые слова: Аналитический, цилиндр, параболический, математический пакет, задача, Maple, *simplify, plots, format*, формат, система.

Abstract. Without a basic mathematical background, a modern graduate of a technical university is unable to effectively solve and analyze scientific, technical, and professional problems arising in their activities. This, in turn, requires a deep knowledge of mathematics, the development of mathematical abilities, as well as the formation of students' professional competence alongside the enhancement of their mathematical skills in solving applied problems. Thus, the purposeful development of mathematical abilities in the process of solving professional tasks is a necessary condition for the effective formation of students' professional competence.

Key words: Cylinder, parabola, mathematical package, Maple, simplification, graphs.

Hozirgi vaqtda fundamental fanlarni o'qitishda o'quv jarayoniga yondashuvni jiddiy qayta ko'rib chiqish, o'qitiladigan fanlarning tarkibi va mazmunini tubdan o'zgartirish talab etiladi. Texnika ixtisosliklari bakalavriatlarining o'quv rejalarida matematika fanlari bo'yicha ma'ruza va amaliy mashg'ulotlar soni fan yo'nalishining mazmuni va chuqurligini saqlab qolish zarurligini hisobga olgan holda sezilarli darajada qisqartirildi. Bunday sharoitda o'quv predmetining mazmunini tanlash va uni shunday tuzish muhim ahamiyatga egaki, materialni o'zlashtirish sifati ta'lim standartining zamonaviy talablariga javob berishi kerak.

“Oliy matematika” kursining “Analitik geometriya” bo‘limida birinchi kursda texnik oliy o‘quv yurtlarida o‘qish boshlanishida fundamental bilimlar poydevori qo‘yilganda talabaning o‘qishga, kelajak kasbiga munosabati alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi, uning faolligi shakllanadi.

Shu sababli, masala texnik yo‘nalish bakalavrlariga "Oliy matematika" kursining "analitik geometriya" bo'limini o'qitish misolida ko'rib chiqaylik. “Oliy matematika” fanini o‘qitish soatlarining keskin qisqarishi sharoitida, umuman olganda, analitik geometriya bo‘yicha o‘quv mashg‘ulotlarini tashkil qilishni o‘zgartirishning aniq yo‘llari taklif etilmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni yechish uchun Maple zamonaviy matematik paketlaridan foydalanish taklif etiladi [6,268 b]. Ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun axborot texnologiyalaridan tizimli foydalanish bilan Maple tizimining imkoniyatlari juda katta. Maple tizimi analitik geometriya va oliy matematikaning matematik analiz sohalaridagi masalalarni tez va aniq, sifatli yechish, shuningdek, 2D va 3D formatlarida animatsion grafik va figuralarni qurish imkoniyatini yaratish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin[4].

1-masala. $y^2 = 4x + 1$ parabolik silindri $z=4-x-y$, $z=0$ va $x=1$ tekisliklar orasidagi bo‘lagining yuzini hisoblang(1-rasm).

Yechish. Izlanayotgan sirt yuzasini hisoblash formulasiga asosan:

$$y^2 = 4x + 1 \text{ sirt tenglamasidan } y = \sqrt{4x+1} \text{ va } dl = \sqrt{\frac{4x+5}{4x+1}} dx$$

$$S_{is} = \int_L [4 - x - y] dl = \int_{-1/4}^1 [4 - x - \sqrt{4x+1}] \sqrt{\frac{4x+5}{4x+1}} dx =$$

$$= -\frac{19}{6} - \frac{9}{4} \ln 2 + \frac{9}{4} \ln(7 + 3\sqrt{5}) + \frac{81\sqrt{5}}{32}$$

Maple dasturi:

> **y:=(x)->sqrt(4*x+1);**

$$y := x \rightarrow \sqrt{4x + 1}$$

> **dl:=simplify(sqrt(1+diff(y(x),x)^2));**

$$dl := \sqrt{\frac{4x + 5}{4x + 1}}$$

> **EI:=Int((4-x-y(x))*dl,x)=int((4-x-y(x))*dl,
x=-1/4..1);**

$$EI := \int \left(4 - x - \sqrt{4x + 1} \right) \sqrt{\frac{4x + 5}{4x + 1}} dx = -\frac{19}{6} - \frac{9}{4} \ln(2)$$

$$+ \frac{9}{4} \ln(7 + 3\sqrt{5}) + \frac{81}{32} \sqrt{5}$$

> **EI:=Int((4-x-y(x))*dl,x)=int((4-x-y(x))*dl,
x=-0.25..1);**

$$EI := \int \left(4 - x - \sqrt{4x + 1} \right) \sqrt{\frac{4x + 5}{4x + 1}} dx = 6.82428682'$$

Sirt va tekisliklarni kesishishi(1-rasm):

> **restart; with(plots):with(plots,intersectplot):**

> **p1:=implicitplot3d({y^2=4*x+1, z=4-x-y},x=-0.5..1,**

y=-3..3, z=0..7, grid=[13,13,13]):

```
> p2:=intersectplot(y^2=4*x+1, z=4-x-y,x=-0.5..1,
y=-3..3, z=0..7, axes=box, thickness=3, orientation=[70,40]);
> p3:=intersectplot(y^2=4*x+1, z=0,x=-0.5..1,y=-3..3, z=0..7, axes=box, thickness=3,
orientation=[70,40]);
> plots[display]([p1,p2,p3],orientation=[70,40]);
Sirt va tekisliklarni kesishishidan hosil bo'lgan bo'lak shakli(2-rasm):
> p1:=intersectplot(y^2=4*x+1, z=4-x-y,x=-0.25..1,
y=-3..3,z=0..7,axes=box,thickness=3,orientation=[70,40]);
> p2:=plot3d(4-x-y,x=-0.25..1,y=-sqrt(4*x+1)..sqrt(4*x+1), axes=normal, filled=true,
orientation=[70,40]);
> plots[display]([p1,p2],orientation=[70,40]);
```


1-rasm.

2-rasm.

2-masala. $4x^2 - y^2 = 4$ giperbolik silindri $z=6-x-y$, $z=0$ va $x=\pm 2$ tekisliklar orasidagi bo'lagining yuzini hisoblang(3-rasm).

Yechish. Izlanayotgan sirt yuzasini (12.1.18) formulaga asosan hisoblaymiz:

1) $x=2$ bo'gandagi giperboloidning o'ng tomon bolagining yuzasini hisoblash:

$$4x^2 - y^2 = 4 \text{ sirt tenglamasidan } y = 2\sqrt{x^2 - 1} \text{ va } dl = \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}} dx.$$

$$S_1 = \int_L [6 - x - y] dl = \int_1^2 [6 - x - 2\sqrt{x^2 - 1}] \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}} dx$$

Maple dasturi:

```
> y:=(x)->2*sqrt(x^2-1);
```

$$y := x \rightarrow 2\sqrt{x^2 - 1}$$

```
> dl:=simplify(sqrt(1+diff(y(x),x)^2));
```

$$dl := \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}}$$

```
> EI:=Int((6-x-y(x))*dl,x)=int((6-x-y(x))*dl,x=1..2.);
```

$$EI := \int \left(6 - x - 2\sqrt{x^2 - 1} \right) \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}} dx = 10.3492437$$

2) $x=-2$ bo'lgandagi giperboloidning chap tomon bolagining yuzasini hisoblash:

$$4x^2 - y^2 = 4 \text{ sirt tenglamasidan } y = -2\sqrt{x^2 - 1} \text{ va } dl = \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}} dx$$

$$S_2 = \int_L [6 - x - y] dl = \int_1^2 [6 - x + 2\sqrt{x^2 - 1}] \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}} dx$$

Maple dasturi:

> **y:=(x)->-2*sqrt(x^2-1);**

$$y := x \rightarrow -2\sqrt{x^2 - 1}$$

> **dl:=simplify(sqrt(1+diff(y(x),x)^2));** $dl := \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}}$

> **EI:=Int((6-x-y(x))*dl,x)=int((6-x-y(x))*dl,x=-2..-1.);**

$$EI := \int \left(6 - x + 2\sqrt{x^2 - 1} \right) \sqrt{\frac{5x^2 - 1}{x^2 - 1}} dx = 33.2085868'$$

Sirt va tekisliklarni kesishishi(3-rasm):

> **restart; with(plots):with(plots,intersectplot):**

> **p1:=implicitplot3d({4*x^2-y^2=4, z=6-x-y},x=-2..2, y=-4..4, z=0..15, grid=[13,13,13]):**

> **p2:=intersectplot(4*x^2-y^2=4, z=6-x-y,x=-2..2,**

y=-4..4, z=0..15, axes=box, thickness=3, orientation=[70,40]):

> **p3:=intersectplot(4*x^2-y^2=4, z=0,x=-1..2,y=-4..4,**

z=0..15, axes=box, thickness=3, orientation=[70,40]):

> **plots[display]([p1,p2,p3],orientation=[70,40]):**

3-rasm.

Bunday masalalarni yechish uchun Maple zamonaviy matematik paketlaridan foydalanish taklif etiladi [1]. Ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etish uchun axborot texnologiyalaridan tizimli foydalanish bilan Maple tizimining imkoniyatlari juda katta. Maple tizimi analitik geometriya va oliy matematikaning matematik analiz sohalaridagi masalalarni tez va aniq, sifatli yechish, shuningdek, 2D va 3D formatlarida animatsion grafik va figuralarni qurish imkoniyatini yaratish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin[3].

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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